

Characterization and Simulation of the Interface Between Continuously and Discontinuously Fiber Reinforced Thermoplastics

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Thermoplastic Co-DiCo FRP

- Material: Polyamide 6 (PA6) + Carbon Fiber
- Process: LFT-D

Thermoplastic Co-DiCo FRP

■ Why CoDiCo?

Thermoplastic Co-DiCo FRP

Water absorption in PA6

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Thermoplastic Co-DiCo FRP

■ Interface characterization

■ Available experiments

■ Normal direction

- Double Cantilever Beam (DCB)
- Climbing Drum Peel Test (CDP)

■ Shear direction

- End Notched Flexure Test (ENF)
- Interlaminar Shear Strength Test (ILSS)

Motivation

Method

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Outlook

Climbing Drum Peel Test

Kinematics

Climbing Drum Peel Test

■ Experimental Setup

Motivation

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Climbing Drum Peel Test

Specimens

Flow direction

- Type A: vacuum dried
- Type B: conditioned at 75% r.H. and 50°C

Climbing Drum Peel Test

Numerical Setup

- Extensive study on material properties (fiber content, orientation, ...)

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HomoPy

Mori-Tanaka

DiCo (continuum)

Halpin-Tsai

Co (laminate)

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Climbing Drum Peel Test

Numerical Setup

- Extensive study on material properties (fiber content, orientation, ...)
- Interface modelled with Cohesive Surface

Motivation

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Results

Experimental: Force over Displacement

Motivation

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Experimental: Force over Displacement

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Results

■ Fractography

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Method

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Results

■ Fractography

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Results

■ Fractography

Results

■ Fractography

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Results

■ Fractography

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Results

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Results

Fractography

Results

■ Experimental Findings:

- Dry interface has lower fracture toughness
 - Alternating ductile/brittle crack propagation leads to lower energy absorption when crack propagates
 - Magnitude of oscillation is increased
- Hypothesis: water absorption allows for enhanced polymer chain mobility and increases elongation at failure, thus ductile fracture is enhanced

Motivation

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Results

Numerical (work in progress):

Motivation

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Results

■ Numerical Findings:

- Energy release rate from experiment can be used in CZ to capture effective behavior
 - Magnitude of oscillations still challenging
- Confirmation that energy release rate is significantly greater with water absorption

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Outlook

■ Experimental:

- Conduct more experiment for different conditioning states
 - Does more water always lead to a greater energy release rate?

■ Numerical:

- Achieve better fitting by conducting numerical studies on the effects of...
 - Mesh size
 - Damage initiation parameter
 - Material parameters of Co and DiCo
 - ...

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References

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Ductile/brittle alternation

